

Gas-Liquid Chromatography :

The GLC of the oil was carried out using chromatograph equipped with thermal conductivity detector and 18 ft carbowax 20M (10%) column. The column and injection part temperatures were maintained at 160° and 200° respectively. Hydrogen was used as carrier gas (40 ml/min). Eighteen peaks obtained in the chromatogram were identified by comparing their relative retention times with those of the authentic samples recorded under identical operating conditions. The percentage of each constituent in the oil was determined by calculating corresponding peak areas. The results are given in the Table.

Thus GLC revealed the presence of seven more compounds, viz., α -pinene, myrcene, γ -terpinene, *p*-cymene, linalyl acetate, bornyl acetate and one unidentified compound in addition to those identified by chemical methods.

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Synthesis and Pharmacology of N-Substituted-4-(*p*-Methoxyphenyl) Piperidine-2,6-diones

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RECENTLY various N-substituted (alkyl, cyclo alkyl and aryl)-4-arylglutarimides have been reported to exhibit antineoplastic activity¹⁻⁷. Pyridine and pyrimidine bases are building blocks of nucleic acids and their various derivatives possess antitumor activity⁸. In view of these observations we synthesized N-heterocyclic-4-(*p*-methoxyphenyl) piperidine-2, 6-diones (IV) as possible antineoplastic agents. In these derivatives pyridine or pyrimidine residues may function as carrier groups. IVg was also prepared to incorporate glycine in the imide structure.

3-(*p*-Methoxyphenyl) glutaric acid (II), prepared by the reduction of corresponding glutaconic acid⁹ (I), was treated with Ac₂O to obtain the glutaric anhydride (III). Heterocyclic amines were condensed with III at

fusion temperature to furnish IVa-g. IR spectrum of IVd showed two peaks at 1690 and 1733 cm⁻¹ characteristic of cyclic imide structure.

Experimental

Melting points were recorded on Gallenkamp m.p. apparatus and are uncorrected. IR spectrum was recorded on Beckmann Acculab-10 Spectrometer.

(IVa) *N*-(4-Pyridyl)-4 (*p*-methoxyphenyl) piperidine-2,6-dione :

III (2.18g, 0.01M) and 4-amino pyridine (1.04g, 0.011M) were mixed and heated to 170-180° with stirring for 30 min. The residue was crystallized from water.

m.p. 163-164°. Yield : 1.6g (53%).

Anal : Found : C, 68.61 ; H, 5.28 ; N, 9.26%

Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₆N₂O₃ : C, 68.84 ; H, 5.43 ; N, 9.44%.

(IVg) 4-(*p*-Methoxyphenyl) piperidine-2, 6-dione-1-acetic acid :

III (2.18g, 0.01M) and glycine (0.75 g, 0.01M) were fused at 180-190° with stirring for 15 min. The dark residue was dissolved in NaHCO₃ solution, and filtered. The filtrate was neutralized with HCl and the regenerated solid was crystallized with water.

m.p. 167-168°. Yield : 2g (71.4%).

Anal : Found : C, 60.78 ; H, 5.53 ; N, 5.13%

Calcd. for C₁₄H₁₅NO₅ : C, 60.64 ; H, 5.45 ; N, 5.05%.

Pharmacology : Compounds IVc, b, d and e (NSC 301435 - 301438) were screened for anticancer activity *in vivo*. Compounds were injected i.p. in saline solution to male mice at doses 400, 200 and 100 mg/kg. The action of the compounds was observed by comparing the median survival time of control and test groups of animals (T/C%) in which P 388 lymphocytic leukemia was induced. The compounds failed to protect the animals from the growth of leukemia. No activity was indicated (% T/C > 140). No toxicity was also observed (as % T/C < 80 and no mortality). % T/C for these compounds are 100 ± 5.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF N-SUBSTITUTED-4-(*p*-METHOXY-PHENYL) PIPERIDINE-2,6-DIONES(IV)

No.	R	m.p. °C	Yield %
IVa	4-Pyridyl	163-164	53
IVb	6-Methyl-2-pyridyl	182-183	43
IVc	3-Methyl-2-pyridyl	141-142	28
IVd	2-Pyrimidyl	176-177	33
IVe	4 Methyl-2-pyrimidyl	184-185	32
IVf	4,6-Dimethyl-2-pyrimidyl	207-208	34
IVg	-CH ₂ -COOH	167-168	71

Elemental analyses of the compound were consistent with their composition.

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Studies on Cycloimmonium Ylides : Synthesis of Some New 2,4,6-Triaryl Pyridines via Pyridinium Ylides

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IN continuation to our previous researches¹⁻² directed towards studies on pyridinium ylides, presently we wish to report herein the synthesis of some new 2,4,6-trisubstituted pyridines having phenyl, naphthyl

and phenanthryl ring attached to the pyridine nucleus which have been achieved by the cyclization reaction of 3-phenanthroylmethylene pyridinium ylide with α , β -unsaturated ketones.

Experimental

Melting points were determined on a Gallen Kamp apparatus and are uncorrected. The IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin Elmer infracord spectrophotometer in KBr phase. The NMR spectra (CDCl₃) were run using A-60 spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard. The products were purified by column chromatography over neutral alumina. The purity was checked by thin layer chromatography using glass plates coated with silica gel 'G' and the spots were detected by placing the tlc plates in iodine chamber.

The pyridinium salt (1) was prepared using the procedure of King *et al*^{7,8}.

Preparation of 2,4,6-triaryl-substituted pyridines (5a-n) :

A mixture of pyridinium salt (1) (3 mmol) and ammonium acetate (3g) in glacial acetic acid (20 ml) was stirred for 30 minutes. To this mixture benzylidene ketone (3a-n) (3 mmol) in glacial acetic acid (10 ml), was added dropwise during 1 hr, after which the temperature was maintained at 120° and heating was continued for additional 4-8 hr. The mixture was left overnight at room temperature and ice cold water (20 ml) was added to precipitate a solid which was separated, washed with methanol, dried and crystallized from appropriate solvent to give 2,4,6-trisubstituted pyridines (5a-n) in 40-75 percent yields (Table 1).

Results and Discussion

3-Phenanthroylmethyl pyridinium salt (1) reacts with a variety of substituted benzylideneacetophenones (3a-e), benzylidene 2-acetonaphthalenes (3f-i) and benzylidene 3-acetophenanthrenes (3j-n) in the presence of ammonium acetate and acetic acid at reflux temperature to give 2,4-di-(substitutedphenyl)-6-(3-phenanthryl)pyridines (5a-e), 4-substitutedphenyl-2-naphthyl-6-(3-phenanthryl) pyridines (5f-i) and 2,6-di-(3-phenanthryl)-4-(substitutedphenyl)pyridines (5j-n) in 40-75 percent yields (Scheme-1).

The course of formation of pyridines from pyridinium ylide has been reported earlier^{3,4}. The ylide (2), which was supposed to be formed by the dehydrohalogenation of pyridinium salt (1), attack on β -carbon atom of α , β -unsaturated ketones (3a-n), yielding new ylide intermediate, pentane-1,5-dionyl pyridinium derivatives (4) which, in turn, underwent cyclization in the presence of ammonium acetate to give 2,4,6-trisubstituted pyridines (5a-n).

The pyridines (5a-n) thus synthesized gave satisfactory elemental analysis and were new. The IR spectra (KBr) showed a characteristic absorption